

Fatigue Strength of Bolting Assemblies made from Stainless Steel subjected to Axial Loads

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ABSTRACT

Bolting assemblies manufactured from stainless steel are becoming more and more important in steel structures. Recent publications show that the relaxation and the associated preload losses are lower than previously expected. This offers opportunities of using preloaded bolting assemblies in a wide range of applications. However, missing design rules and insufficient data basis on the fatigue strength of stainless steel bolting assemblies limit their application. Neither Eurocode 3 for structural engineering nor VDI 2230 - Part 1 for mechanical engineering provide sufficient regulations for the fatigue resistant design of stainless steel bolts.

This paper presents new and extensive fatigue test results on stainless steel bolting assemblies in comparison with bolting assemblies made from carbon steel (e. g. HV system with and without hot-dip galvanisation). In total 224, fatigue tests were performed at a constant mean load in the finite life region to determine a detail category according to EN 1993-1-9. Hereby, the effects of the nominal size M6, M12 and M20, of the strength grade 80 and 100 and of the microstructure conditions austenitic (A4) and ferritic-austenitic (D8) were investigated. Tests on a smaller scope (n = 90) should clarify the effect of lubrication conditions the fatigue life using both liquid and solid lubricants. A statistical evaluation according to Eurocode 3 led to a classification into a detail category for bolting assemblies subjected to normal stress.

Keywords: stainless steel bolts, fatigue testing, detail category, Eurocode 3

1 INTRODUCTION

Stainless steel is becoming more important in mechanical engineering, steel structures, maritime and offshore sectors due to its corrosion, acid and temperature resistance. Components made of stainless steel require fasteners that are also corrosion-resistant, and due to installation reliability and maintenance, usually bolting assemblies are used. Cyclically loaded components require high-strength preloaded joints (1), whose durability with respect to the applied preload level has been proven in recent research studies (2). The verification of fatigue strength is an essential design criterion for steel structures. However, the knowledge about fatigue strength in the finite life region and at endurance limit ($N > 2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles) of stainless steel bolts is insufficient due to the low number of fatigue tests reported in the literature, difficulty in comparing results due to varied test conditions (3; 4; 5) or the outdated database (6).

The lack of knowledge about the axial fatigue strength of stainless steel bolt-nut joints leads to normative deficits compared to carbon steel bolts. This can cause uncertainties in the fatigue design

of bolted joints using stainless steel bolts, as defined in existing standards such as VDI 2230-1 (7), particularly in the endurance limit. The VDI 2230-1 (7) for mechanical engineering provides no specific recommendations regarding the fatigue resistance of stainless steel bolts subjected to cyclic axial loads. In Eurocode 3 (EN 1993-1-9 (8)) it is not excluded that detail category (DC) 50 is also used for bolts made from stainless steel, although no experimentally determined data was used in the Eurocode 3 Background Document (9). In the draft for revision of Eurocode 3 (prEN1993-1-9 (10)), the detail categories are limited entirely to bolts and rods made of carbon steel. In particular, the verification in very high cycle fatigue application can lead to uncertainties due to the lack of knowledge. This paper presents new results from axial fatigue tests on common bolting assemblies made of carbon and stainless steel (*Fig. 1*). Furthermore, fatigue tests on the effect of the lubrication condition are also presented.

Fig. 1. Bolting assemblies tested on fatigue: bolts and nuts according to ISO 4014/ISO (M6 – M12), HV bolting assemblies (M12 – M20) and bolting assemblies from stainless steels (M6-M20)

2 FATIGUE STRENGTH ACCORDING TO EUROCODE 3

The verification against fatigue failure according to **EN 1993-1-9** (8) is usually performed with the nominal stress concept ($\Delta\sigma_{Ed} \leq \Delta\sigma_{Rd}$). On the resistance side, the DC50 (Constructional detail 14, Tab. 8.1 (8)) is to be applied for bolts subjected to normal stress, corresponding to a characteristic reference value of fatigue resistance $\Delta\sigma_C = 50$ MPa with a probability of survival $P_s = 95\%$ at $N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. The slope parameter of the fatigue strength curve is $m = 3$ up to the fatigue endurance limit ($\Delta\sigma_D$) at $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. For bolt diameters larger than 30 mm, the size effect must be considered by the reduction factor k_s . The DC50, which is currently valid according to Eurocode 3 (EC3), Parts 1-9 (8) applies equally to bolts and rods with threads rolled or cut. In addition, the time of thread forming (threads rolled before or after heat treatment), the mean load level due to preload and additional bolt load due to operation as well as the surface or corrosion protection layer are not explicitly considered. Accordingly, the fatigue strength must be understood as a lower limit. The recommendation of the DC50 of EC3 (8) was only derived from the database of carbon steel bolts (9), although the EC3 can be formally used for the fatigue-resistant design of components and bolted joints made from stainless steel.

The current draft for revision of EC3 **prEN 1993-1-9** (10) divides the fatigue strength of bolts and rods subjected to normal stress into four DCs made from carbon steel only. The highest DC71 is used for uncoated black bolts with threads rolled after heat treatment. DC56 is applied for bolts and rods with threads rolled before heat treatment without coating. DC50 is defined as the lower limit for bolts and rods with threads rolled before heat treatment and additional hot-dip (hdg) and electric galvanisation, and also for cut threads. In addition, the size effect (resp. the effect of the reduction factor k_s) for carbon steel bolts $>M30$ with hot-dip or electric galvanisation is reduced by decreasing the exponent from 0.25 to 0.1 (1; 11; 12). The prEN 1993-1-9 (10) recommends a shift of the knee point from $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ to $N_D = N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. This is consistent with VDI 2230 - Part 1 (7) for mechanical engineering.

Furthermore, stainless steel bolts with sufficient strength are considered to have the same fatigue strength as carbon bolts with threads rolled before heat treatment. The positive effect of work hardening in the thread root, which increases fatigue strength as in carbon steel bolts with threads rolled after heat treatment, does not apply to stainless steel bolts (6; 7; 13).

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

The experimental investigations focus on bolting assemblies made from carbon steel as reference specimens, as well as bolting assemblies made from stainless steel. In order to investigate the size effect, the dimensions M6, M12 and M20 were tested. An influence of the strength is not initially expected due to the sharp notch effect for carbon steel bolting assemblies. However, to confirm this assumption, the strength grades 8.8 and 10.9 were analysed. For stainless steel bolting assemblies, the strength grades A4-80, A4-100 and D8-100 were included in the test program. Bolts according to ISO 4014 (14) with corresponding nuts according to ISO 4032 (15) and washers according to ISO 7089 (16) were used. Geometric and surface layer effects from hdg were examined on HV-bolts in accordance with EN 14399-4/-6 (17; 18). The investigated bolting assemblies are shown in *Fig. 1*. *Table 2* also contains an overview of the test scope and the results of the statistical evaluation according to Eurocode 3 Background Document (9) for the probabilities of survival $P_S = 50\%$ and $P_S = 95\%$ as well as the constant and free slope parameters of the test-assisted S-N curves.

3.1 Mechanical technological properties

Each series has been tested for normative deviations regarding mechanical-technological properties according to ISO 898-1/-2 (19; 20) for carbon steel resp. ISO 3506-1/-2 (21; 22) for stainless steel bolting assemblies. For this purpose, the mechanical-technological properties, such as chemical composition, core hardness, microhardness profile as well as the microstructure, coating and surface layer condition were characterised in (23). Due to the large amount of data, a complete presentation in the present article had to be omitted.

The mechanical-technological properties and the chemical composition of all tested bolting assemblies fulfilled the normative specifications.

3.2 Torque tightening tests

The friction coefficients in the thread μ_{th} are of interest, since it is intended to correlate them with the observed increase in fatigue resistance due to the reduction of local stresses in the highly stressed first load bearing bolt thread by facilitated relative movement (13; 24). Therefore, torque/clamp force tests according to ISO 16047 (25) and EN 14399-2 (26) are performed on bolting assemblies made from stainless steel (series #09 - #11) in the condition as delivered (*Table 1*).

The experimental studies were carried out on a KISTLER test system. To determine the friction coefficients as well as the related scatter within the test sample, the investigations were carried out by a defined testing procedure. The tightening speed was 5 min^{-1} throughout (25; 27).

Only the friction coefficients in the threads μ_{th} will be analysed for further fatigue studies. The friction beams are plotted in diagrams of thread torque T_{th} related to the corresponding clamp load, respectively preload F (*Fig. 2*). An approximately linear trace up to a high utilisation can be observed for the most specimens. By increasing the clamp load and therefore the utilisation, nearly all traces become more progressive in the last third, due to higher friction.

In *Table 1* significant values of the friction coefficient in the thread at a certain mean load F_m are summarised. The statistical evaluation in *Table 1* delivers an indication of the scatter. As a measure of scatter, the minimum coefficient of variation V_x can be determined for the series #11 (M12 D8-100). It must be mentioned, that an outlier was identified by a probability plot and excluded from the evaluation. The scatter as well as the range of friction coefficient μ_{th} differ significantly, depending on the tested bolting assemblies. The maximum coefficient of friction $\mu_{th} = 0.212$ as well as the maximum scatter are observed in the series #10.

Fig. 2. a) M12 A4-80 (series #09), b) M12 A4-100 (series #10) and c) M12 D8-100 (series #11)

A comparison and evaluation of the determined friction coefficients with published values is difficult, considering the small number of available data. The articles (2; 5; 28) do not publish the evaluation of the individual friction coefficients in the thread and the bearing. For solid paste MOLYKOTE 1000 lubricated studs of dimension M16 and M20, both grade A4-80 (5; 29) provide minimal friction coefficients $\mu_{th} = 0.145$ respectively $\mu_{th} = 0.103$. This lubrication does not suit a direct comparison to waxed surfaces. However, it underlines the low friction values of series #11 (Table 1) to some extent.

Table 1. Statistical evaluation of the torque/clamp force testing

#	Bolting assembly	#data	lubrication	clamping length l_k [mm]	F_m [kN]	m_x	s_x	μ_{th}		
								V_x [%]	min	max
09	M12 A4-80	5	waxed	40	37.77	0.149	0.048	19.46	0.117	0.208
10	M12 A4-100	5		40	53.11	0.131	0.039	29.77	0.086	0.212
11	M12 D8-100	5	as delivered	40		0.065	0.006	8.64	0.057	0.075

3.3 Fatigue tests

According to the specifications of DIN 969 (30), the testing devices were adjusted and successfully verified for suitability before the fatigue test. A ratio of bending stress σ_b to normal stress σ_{ax} below 6 % was verified. All fatigue tests were performed at the *University of Applied Sciences* in Wismar according to DIN 969 (30) at a constant mean load F_m with varying R-ratios using either the dynamic resonance (M6 – M12) (Fig. 3) or servo hydraulic (M20) testing system in force-controlled mode. The test frequency was between 112 Hz (resonance) respective 10 - 50 Hz (servo-hydraulic). The temperature of the bolting assemblies was measured during the test at a representative number of samples and was always below $T < 50^\circ\text{C}$. The fatigue tests were carried out at a constant amplitude loading (CAL) in the finite life region of the S-N curve. The test ended with the fracture of the bolts in two parts or by reaching a number of cycles $N = 5 \cdot 10^6$ without failure (i. e., run out (D)). The stress ratio varies between $0.47 \leq R < 0.80$. The mean load ($F_m = 0.7 \cdot R_{p0.2, \min} \cdot A_{s, \text{nom}}$) utilises the minimum

normative 0.2 % proof stress $R_{p0.2,min}$ of the bolt material in the stress cross section $A_{s,nom}$ by 70 %. The 0.2 % proof stresses $R_{p0.2}$ of the stainless steel bolts, as determined from the tensile tests, are comparable to these of the carbon steel bolts. To ensure comparability, the stainless steel bolting assemblies were tested at the same mean stress level as the carbon steel bolting assemblies. The carbon steel bolting assemblies were tested with slightly oiled bolts and/or nuts and the stainless steel bolts were tested with a waxed surface. For the tests to determine a DC according to EC3 Background Document (9) no additional lubrication was added.

Resonance testing machine and device for bolts M6 - M12

Results from statistical evaluation according to EN 1993-1-9 Background

Fig. 4 contains the S-N diagrams of all 12 series separately with the corresponding plotted S-N curves of the statistical evaluation according to EC3 Background Document (9) with probabilities of survival $P_S = 50\%$ (coloured full line) and $P_S = 95\%$ (coloured dashed line) for a constant slope parameter $m = 3$. The recommended DCs ($\Delta\sigma_C$ at $N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles) according to prEN 1993-1-9 (10) (resp. additional DCs for comparison) are plotted as a black solid line. The **carbon steel** series #01 (M6 8.8) has a fatigue strength (DC80) at the same level as series #02 (M12 8.8) which is from the authors' view due to not comparable lubrication conditions between both test series. Hence, the expected size effect according to VDI 2230-1 (7) did not occur. Between series #02 (M12 8.8; DC80) and #03 (M12 10.9; DC71), there is an unexpected strength effect in favour of strength grade 8.8. Series #01 - #03 and test data could be classified into DC80 respective DC71. Despite the larger bolt dimension, series #04 (M20 10.9; DC71) with threads rolled after heat treatment has a fatigue strength comparable to series #03 with smaller bolt size (M12 10.9; DC71) with threads rolled before heat treatment and fulfil the recommendation of DC71 according to prEN 1993-1-9 (10). This can be explained by the fatigue strength-increasing characteristics of the manufacture process "threads rolled after heat treatment" (13). The series #05 (HV M12 10.9), a carbon steel HV bolting assembly, reached the DC63 due the missing hdg. This is in line with the recommendations for uncoated black HV-bolting assemblies up to the dimension M30 without size reduction (1). The reduction compared to DC71 for M12 ISO-bolting assemblies for machinery is attributed to the higher notch effect resulting from the load distribution conditions in the engaged threads. The lower nut height in combination with the larger width across flats increases the notch effect in the first load-bearing thread and must therefore be considered with a 10 % reduction in fatigue strength at endurance limit acc. to VDI 2230-1 (7). Series #06 (HV M12 10.9 hdg) reached the lowest DC50 due to the fatigue-reducing hdg. The HV bolting assemblies (Series #05, #06, #07) reached the recommended DCs from (1; 12). All carbon steel bolts from series #01 to #07 consistently failed in the first load-bearing thread (A).

The most significant size effect of **stainless steel** bolts can be observed from M6 (series #08) with DC90 to M12 (series #09) with DC71. The size effect decreases from M12 (series #10; DC63 and #11; DC71) to M20 (series #12; DC56). The austenitic series #10 (M12 A4-100) reached a lower DC63 than the austenitic-ferritic series #11 (M12 D8-100) of the same strength grade with DC71. Strength grade 80 (series #09, M12) with the same nominal size and steel group achieved a higher DC71 than strength grade 100 (series #10, M12) with DC63. The stainless steel bolting assemblies (series #09 - #12) have lower fatigue strengths compared to carbon steel bolting assemblies (series #02 - #03), but higher fatigue strengths than the HV bolting assemblies (series #05 - #07) for the corresponding nominal sizes. Fractures occurred in the first load-bearing thread (A) and at the transition between shank and head (B) for stainless steel bolts with strength grade 80. This is in line with the findings from Stranghöner and Ehrhardt (5) on bolting assemblies M20 A4-80. Stainless steel bolts with strength grade 100 consistently failed in the first load-bearing thread (A). From a first look, the DCs for the series #08 (M6 A4-80), #09 (M12 A4-80) and #11 (M12 D8-100) provide a good agreement with DC 71 of the recommendation of prEN 1993-1-9 (10) for carbon steel bolting assemblies with threads rolled after heat treatment. However, series #10 (M12 A4-100) and #12 (M20 A4-100) confirm the findings of Wiegand et al. (6) that stainless steel bolts have equivalent fatigue strength to carbon steel bolts with threads rolled before heat treatment and can therefore be classified as DC56 according to prEN 1993-1-9 (10). However, the further reduction in fatigue strength for larger nominal sizes > M20 has not been investigated. It should also be noted that according to fatigue tests at constant amplitude loading up to $N = 10^7$ load cycles by Glienke et al. (23), stainless steel bolts do not have the significant endurance limit of carbon bolts!

Table 2. Results from the statistical evaluation acc. to the Background Document to EN 1993-1-9 (9)

#series bolting assemblies	#data	slope [-]		$\Delta\sigma_{c,PS=95\%}$ [MPa]		detail category
		m _{var}	m _{const.}	var.	const.	
bolt/nut assemblies - carbon steel according to ISO 4014/ISO 4032						
01 M6x70 8.8 - uncoated black ¹⁾	15	3.61		105.4 (116.6)	88.7 (100.6)	80
02 M12x70 8.8 - uncoated black ¹⁾	15	3.97		112.3 (120.1)	84.7 (101.9)	80
03 M12x70 10.9 - uncoated black ¹⁾	18	3.42	3	85.4 (94.9)	75.8 (85.5)	71
04 M20x120 10.9 - uncoated black ²⁾	31	3.99		99.0 (112.5)	75.3 (90.8)	71
bolt/nut assemblies - carbon steel according to EN 14399-4/-6						
05 HV M12x60 10.9 - uncoated black ¹⁾	10	3.29		72.2 (83.7)	68.8 (79.2)	63
06 HV M12x60 10.9 - hdg ¹⁾	10	3.43	3	60.2 (67.7)	53.2 (61.3)	50
07 HV M20x120 10.9 - hdg ¹⁾	28	2.80		54.5 (60.1)	57.9 (63.5)	56
bolt/nut assemblies - stainless steel according to ISO 4014/ISO 4032						
08 M6x70 A4-80 ³⁾	14	3.55		106.3 (122.8)	93.3 (108.2)	90
09 M12x70 A4-80 ³⁾	14	3.50		86.7 (97.9)	75.4 (86.6)	71
10 M12x70 A4-100 ³⁾	29	3.31	3	73.3 (80.4)	66.7 (72.3)	63
11 M12x70 D8-100 ³⁾	16	2.43		63.0 (70.3)	76.2 (85.5)	71
12 M20x140 A4-100 ³⁾	24	3.63		73.0 (82.3)	60.1 (71.7)	56
1) Threads rolled before heat treatment						
2) Threads rolled after heat treatment						
3) Threads rolled due cold working						
$\Delta\sigma_{c,PS=95\%}$	Reference value of fatigue strength with probability of survival $P_S = 95\%$					
(...)	$P_S = 50\%$ probability of survival					

Fig. 4. S-N curves resulting from statistical evaluation according to Eurocode 3 Background Document (9) of bolting assemblies of carbon steel according to ISO 4014 a) – d); of carbon steel according to EN 14399-4 e) – g); of stainless steel according to ISO 4014 h) – l)

3.3.1 Effect of lubrication on the fatigue strength

The effect of the lubrication systems was estimated on test series #01, #02, #03, #08, #09, #10, #11 in four lubrication conditions: unlubricated (black), as-delivered, bonded coating (grey) and oiled (red). The unlubricated condition is used as a reference with a high coefficient of friction in the threads μ_{th} . The effects of lubrication on fatigue strength are investigated in the consideration of Kraemer's hypotheses (24). For this purpose, oil is used as a lubrication in order to investigate the influence of supporting effects due to the capillary effect of liquid lubricants and thus the inhibition of crack growth. The use of bonded coating investigates the effect of increased stress distribution by reducing friction coefficients in the threads μ_{th} .

The uncoated black carbon steel bolts and nuts were oiled and the stainless steel bolts were waxed in the condition as delivered by the manufacturer. First, all other bolts and nuts were cleaned by hand and afterwards with ethanol for the unlubricated condition respective in preparation for lubrication with oil and bonded coating. Two drops of BALLISTOL universal oil were applied on the bolt threads for oiled lubrication. The bonded coating smartGLEIT LS808 was only applied to the bolt threads in two layers. Five specimens each were tested on the 2nd stress horizon. A pragmatic approach was chosen for this. The statistical evaluation was carried out to estimate the mean S-N curve for each lubrication system with a probability of survival $P_s = 50\%$ and fixed slope parameter shown in Fig. 5 with the individual fractures. For this purpose, the mean fatigue life of the five specimens with lubrication on the 2nd stress horizon was determined as the centre of gravity. Then the mean S-N curves ($P_s = 50\%$) of the test series with a full sample size (#01 - #03, #08 - #11, cf. Fig. 4) were moved to this centre of gravity of the lubrication tests with a constant slope of $m = 3$.

For the carbon steel bolting assemblies (series #02 and #03), the unlubricated condition and the bonded coating resulted in a significant lower fatigue strength than the delivery conditions and oil lubrication, which have nearly the same fatigue strength. All bolts failed due to fracture in the first load-bearing thread (A). This in line with the findings from Kraemer (24).

Fig. 5 S-N curves (50 % probability of survival) with different lubrications conditions

The fatigue strength of the stainless steel bolting assemblies was significantly increased when lubricated with oil, compared to the unlubricated and bonded coating conditions. The wax coating in its as-delivered condition did not significantly increase the fatigue strength of series #08, #10 and #11, compared to the unlubricated condition. However, for series #09, the wax coating had a positive effect on the fatigue strength. It can be concluded that a low friction coefficient in the thread μ_{th} , e. g. due to the wax coating or the bonded coating, does not have any significant fatigue strength-increasing characteristics, as described in (13; 24).

Fractures in series #10 and #11 were mostly located in the failure location (A). However, if the oil increases the fatigue strength of the threads in series #08 and #09, the failure location changed to fractures in the head-shank transition (B). When the threads of strength grade A4-80 are uncoated the fractures only occur in the first load-bearing thread (A) due to reduced fatigue of the thread.

3.4 Fractographic investigations on fracture surfaces

Fig. 6 shows the macroscopic and microscopic fracture surfaces of series #10 (a - c) and #11 (d - f) to fractographically investigate the austenitic (A4) or austenitic-ferritic (D8) steel group. Both specimens were subjected to the same stress level of $\Delta\sigma = 100$ MPa and failed in the first load-bearing thread (A) with comparable numbers of load cycles at fracture ($N_f = 100,211$ load cycles respective $N_f = 142,401$ load cycles).

Fig. 6 Fracture surfaces of stainless steel bolts series #10 (a, b, c) and series #11 (d, e, f)

Macroscopically, the specimen from series #10 has a smaller fatigue fracture surface (A) and a larger ductile fracture surface (B) than the specimen from series #11. Both specimens show several cracks in the thread root, which are characterised by crack steps at different fracture heights. Fig. 6 a) and d) each show microscopic images of the fatigue fracture surface (A) using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Fatigue striations can be recognised in a). In d) a crack step and the surface of the thread root are shown. In addition, the edge of the fracture surface has a finer fatigue fracture structure than in the middle of the fatigue fracture, due to the stretched microstructure of the threads resulting from work hardening. Fig. 6 c) and 6 f) show the ductile fracture surfaces (B) with spherical dimples characteristic.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The fatigue tests carried out on carbon steel bolting assemblies confirmed that the classification of the DC in the draft for revision of EC3 (prEN 1993-1-9 (10)) for carbon steel bolts is reliable, whereby for uncoated black bolts with threads rolled before heat treatment, DC 63 with $k_s = (30/d)^{0.1}$ for $d > M30$ according to (1) is more appropriate. The derivation of DCs for stainless steel bolts cannot

be finalised on the basis of the available data. Nevertheless, important findings can be extracted based on the previously unpublished data of this paper. There is an effect of size, which is particularly apparent between the bolt dimensions M6 and M12. Stainless steel bolts made of duplex steel (austenitic-ferritic) reach higher fatigue strengths than austenitic bolts. Compared to carbon steel bolts, stainless steel bolts can be classified in higher DC than HV bolting assemblies with hdg. At this point, further investigations on the effect of mean stress and size effect would be beneficial.

The effect of lubrication on the fatigue strength of both carbon steel and stainless steel bolts indicates that significantly higher fatigue strengths are achieved with sufficient oil lubrication compared to the unlubricated condition or bonded coatings. In addition, no significant positive effect of the reduction in thread friction, as described in (13) and (24), could be observed.

Further investigations on the fatigue strength of stainless steel bolts would be preferable at the endurance limit. This is due to the shift of the knee point from $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ to $N_C = N_D = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles according to the current draft for revision of EC3 (10) and the findings according to Glienke et al. (23), which did not determine fatigue resistance at endurance limit. This could lead to uncertainties in the design.

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